

Towards the Digital Product Passport: the potential contribution to standardization from TRICK project

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SUMMARY

The inputs to standardization presented in this document derive from the main results of the TRICK project and are related to several topics addressed during its activities.

Traceability and Digital Product Passport (DPP), sustainability and environmental impacts, circularity, market surveillance and anticounterfeiting are the areas on which the project gives a clear and, in some cases, tangible contribution. Thanks to its standardized approach and to the experimentation on its industrial pilots, the project produced some valuable outputs for enhancing standardization and standards adoption in real life of industry.

In some cases, the need for standardization initiatives arose widely, such as in the case of circularity assessment or in anticounterfeiting and anomaly detection. Furthermore, criticalities in the existing methodologies were put in evidence thanks to the pilot's application, as in the PEF studies execution.

TRICK's standardized approach to data collection along the supply chain and its data model, based on a significant extension of the CEN CWA 16667 eBIZ specification and on methodologies from EPCIS and UNECE, could represent an important instrument to support companies that will have to comply with the incoming regulations (EPR, ESPR and DPP).

The results and ready-to-use resources coming from the activities on traceability and sustainability data collection will be subject of the new CEN Workshop Agreement based on TRICK results, that is launched on December 2024.

Introduction

Thanks to the activity carried out by TRICK consortium throughout the project, several insights have been gathered on how TRICK results can impact on standards and regulation already in place, highlighting where new standards or common methodologies are needed.

The results of the two PEF¹ studies, conducted by ENEA on two products made during the pilot phase of the project (a high-quality wool coat and a work uniform) have pointed out relevant observations to the current draft of the PEF Category Rules (PEFCRs) “Apparel and footwear”² under development at European level, highlighting some criticalities and shortcomings. Similarly, the activities done on the assessment of the circularity of materials, with the application of the MCI indicator to the TRICK pilots, highlighted the need for common standardized methods for circularity assessment. Their adoption could positively affect the application of the most used indicators and contribute to overcome ambiguities of the collected results.

Valuable insight comes also from the results of the service supporting the request of Preferential Certificate of Origin (PCO), developed and tested with the involvement of the Italian Customs agency (ADM). The interoperability between TRICK platform and AIDA system of ADM, with the support of the Blockchain technology, facilitates and speeds up data exchange between all stakeholders, improves traceability and transparency of the supply chain, reduces disputes on transactions and trade and allows to manage at batch level the shipments documentation of goods. A new model of collaboration with Customs systems on PCO certifications is proposed, based on the use of blockchain technologies to check, in a new modality of control, the validity of documentation presented to support the customs declaration.

This policy brief in its first section is focused on the contribution to the data collection for the Digital Product Passport provided by TRICK projects with its data model and tools and semantics. Moreover, the new initiative on the CEN Workshop Agreement based on TRICK results is presented in Chapter 2.

1 The contribution to data collection for the Digital Product Passport

The last news about the Digital Product Passport, at the time of writing, says that for clothing it will become mandatory in 2027. In a cascading effect, companies in the supply chains will be required to provide the necessary and faithful data to the brands, so a big effort must be carried out to put such companies of Textile and Clothing, especially SMEs, in the condition to comply with the incoming requirements of their customers.

In this context, the potential contribution of the TRICK project to a framework of standards supporting the data collection behind the Digital Product Passport (DPP) is very relevant.

¹ Product Environmental Footprint
² <https://pefapparelfootwear.eu/>

The TRICK data model, with its holistic and standardized approach to the collection and management of both traceability and sustainability data along the whole supply chain, is one of the main results of TRICK, with an interesting mapping towards the DPP requirements.

The experience of TRICK project, with its industrial pilots (one for classic fashion garment and one for technical protective workwear), highlights two relevant criticalities that companies have to face to set up new collaborations with brands with the involvement of third-party platform: on one side, the lack of interfaces, on the company systems, to exchange data with external platforms (like TRICK); on the other side, the absence of a standard, or of a standardized approach, that would ensure homogeneity in data collection across the supply chains made of a number of different companies.

In the fragmented supply chains of the TC sector the big challenge is to find the way to keep costs to comply with the upcoming regulations low and affordable, particularly for SMEs. The solution could be creating a standardized and open language to collect data across the layers of supply chain.

The work carried out on the data collection along the supply chain, and tested on the two TC pilots, during TRICK project has always been driven by a careful analysis of the available standards to define the semantics and the data model and to be aligned with the current regulations. The CEN CWA eBIZ16667 specification framework was chosen as a basis for building the TRICK data model, while the approach to traceability followed the UNECE methodology indications and the EPCIS GS1 event model were chosen as reference to develop the so-called traceability “enriched event-based model”³.

TRICK data model has a holistic approach to put together in the same logical framework both daily operation information and traceability and sustainability information, in order to enable the coherence between the digital and the virtual representation of the product life cycle. Transparency and confidentiality of data are guaranteed by the blockchain-enabled governance model of the platform, that ensures the security and reliability of the data. The TRICK data model integrates in its public information schema also the references and “hash” fingerprints necessary to create synergies with blockchain infrastructures and guarantee the data integrity.

The implementation of the TRICK data model in the [eBIZ Document factory](#), with the management of traceability and sustainability data not managed in the last official version of the specification, led to the proposal of a massive extension to eBIZ to support the traceability issues and the problem of collecting data necessary to fuel any environmental impact evaluation (such as PEF and circularity assessment).

During the project’s life the regulatory landscape has evolved significantly. However, the TRICK platform's adaptability to these new regulations highlights its long-term vision. A significant effort was spent to be aligned with the indication coming from the ESPR⁴ and EPR⁵ regulation, with constant attention to the requirements of the DPP being defined.

³ For more details see the deliverable D2.2 at <https://mydisk.cs.upc.edu/s/SqZMtjmtGGEJkMm>

⁴ [Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation](#)

⁵ Extended Producer Responsibility

2 TRICK next step on DPP: a new CEN Workshop Agreement on TRICK results

On December 5th, 2024, the kick off meeting⁶ of the new CEN⁷ Workshop Agreement on **Guidelines for data collection from Textile and Clothing supply chains for the Digital Product Passport (DPP)** based on TRICK project results takes place.

“A CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA) is an experimental technical document developed rapidly with the discussion and contribution of all interested parties, with the same mechanisms of transparency and consensus as in voluntary standardization. They are therefore particularly suitable for sharing innovative know-how and quickly transferring the results of Research and Innovation projects to the market”⁸.

Thus, this initiative is the occasion to formalise the TRICK contribution to the world of standardisation with a pre-normative result according to the scheme foreseen by CEN to this purpose.

For the TRICK project it is the occasion for sharing its results from the experience in the field regarding the data models and the flows of information, but also in terms of reference collaborative processes between the supply chain actors and the terminology and coding.

As the CEN Workshop model is an open and public procedure for sharing a result or a know-how, the promoter expect that also other stakeholders can share their experience and could contribute to the final outcomes; on this purpose other initiatives dealing with circularity, sustainability and digital product passport (like the projects of the ECOSYSTEX network and the ETP network) have been contacted in order to give their contribution from their own outcomes.

The main objective of this CWA is to establish guidelines to enable and optimize data collection along textile and clothing supply chains, improving traceability, transparency and sustainability claims, in line with European regulations and strategies.

The CWA will aim at facilitating the collection and validation of information along the highly fragmented supply chains in Textile and Clothing sector. The activity of such data collection is essential for effectively supporting the declarations that ESPR regulation and Digital Product Passport (DPP) will require.

In a period when a number of standardization efforts are in place, the aim of this CWA is to cover a gap between the current practices in textile and clothing supply chains and their expected behaviours when the ESPR regulations will be fully in force.

The TRICK project builds upon the eBIZ specification for textiles (see in www.ebiz-tcf.eu and CEN CWA 16667) its proposal for data flows on traceability and sustainability aims at its

⁶ See CEN announcement at <https://www.cencenelec.eu/news-and-events/news/2024/workshop/2024-10-30-trick/>

⁷ The European Committee for Standardization is one of three European Standardization Organizations (together with CENELEC and ETSI) that have been officially recognized by the European Union and by the European Free Trade Association (EFTA) as being responsible for developing and defining voluntary standards at European level.

⁸ Definition from <https://www.uni.com/en/standardisation/innovation/>

extension in an **open and public process** In a period when a number of standardization efforts are in place, the aim of this CWA is to cover a gap between the current practices in textile and clothing supply chains and their expected behaviours when the ESPR regulations will be fully in force.

Contributions are expected from other initiatives and projects as collaboration have been already established with the European projects [PESCO-UP](#), [CISUTAC](#) and [CircThread](#) to provide a complete vision of the circular supply chain.

The TRICK CWA will be a valuable public resource for companies' decision makers, IT solutions providers, experts in sustainability, as well as industry trade organizations, industry policymakers and, in general, all the stakeholders in the ecosystem around the textile and clothing supply chains (like logistic operators or auditors, waste collectors and recyclers).

3 Policy implications and Recommendations

More in general the experiences from textile and technical pilots and the insights gained from the platform testing highlight some lessons learned from the demonstration of TRICK platform in real TC business environment and might be a valuable contribution to the formulation of the DPP delegated act for textile. Since DPP will leverage a subset of the data collected by TRICK, these conclusions can contribute to highlight the effort still to be carried out to put the companies of TC, especially SMEs, in the condition to be ready for the implementation of the incoming DPP regulation.

The need for internal **digitalization** and **standardization** along the entire supply chain is the first outcome resulting from TRICK experience, necessary to facilitate the rapid, reliable and cost-effective data collection for the DPP.

Guidelines for data insertion, enhanced data centralization and digitization, standardized data groups to avoid misinterpretation, automated data transfer processes and portability: these are the main insights included in the set of recommendations provided by the project.

The benefits and priorities coming from the lessons learned thanks to the TRICK project are shown in the Fig.1⁹.

	Traditional TC	Technical TC	Stakeholders	Data management	PEF	TRICK
						Positive impact
Data collection difficulty and cost	1	1	1	4	1	
Reliability of data	2	2	3	3	2	
Data transfer and portability	3	3	4	2	6	
Lack of standardisation	5	5	2	1	5	
Technological Integration and Automation	4	4	5	5	7	
Confidentiality vs Public Disclosure	6	6	7	6	4	
Policy Implications	7	7	6	7	3	

Fig. 1 Benefits and priorities coming from the lessons learned by TRICK project¹⁰

⁹ More details in deliverables D5.6, D5.8, D7.6 and D7.7 in <https://www.trick-project.eu/project-documents>

¹⁰ Figure from Chapter 5 of the deliverable D5.6 – Performance evaluation of Textile Clothing pilot

The lack of standardization for the data management is a critical issue: companies are already able to collect data, but in absence of standardized guidelines the information is often not comparable and characterized by different levels of granularity.

The new CEN CWA on TRICK results has been proposed to try to overcome this issue, providing companies with a shared and standardized set of instruments to help them be ready for the implementation of the Digital Product Passport.